

FEATURES OF THE SOFT POWER BODIES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The given article presents the development of the concept of “soft power” in Uzbekistan from its inception so far. The features of the potential of “soft power” in Uzbekistan are given. Recommendations based on foreign experience are given for the development of “soft power” in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: “soft power”, diplomacy, education, culture, sports, tourism.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to suggest that the concept of "soft power", which is discovered by Joseph Nye in the 20th century is considered as an integral part of international relations. States rely on soft power to establish relationships and gain trust, and a state's position and influence internationally are also determined by its soft power. According to Timofey Kolgushkin, a professor at the Peoples' Friendship University of Russia, "soft power" determines the influence a country can have on others. Soft power can be used to achieve a specific goal in international relations. “Soft power” is a model of achieving desired results based on voluntary participation, sympathy and attractiveness. Soft power means peacefully solving problems and signing agreements. In this era of freedom, democracy and the rule of law, the use of soft power is very important. At present time countries actively using this model include the USA, Great Britain, France, Italy, Japan and North Korea. Until the end of the 20th century, “hard power” played the main role in international politics, but by the 21st century “soft power” was able to take the main place. Today in any country, be it the United States or any other, the ability to influence others is limited.

Definitely, soft power is based on education, culture and sports. The areas of diplomacy and tourism occupy a special place. Cultural and scientific connections are established with students and scientists from other countries through a quality education system, international exchange programs and scholarships. The country's educational standards and values are shared internationally. “Art, music, literature and cinema showcase the country's rich cultural heritage and contemporary culture. Through international sporting events, competitions and games, athletes glorify the name of the country throughout the world. Through diplomacy, political and economic relations are strengthened, peace and harmony are ensured. “Diplomacy is one of the most important means of solving the problems that war can cause by peaceful means.” Soft power refers to the influence a country can have on others and its reputation in their eyes.

Characteristics of soft power and public diplomacy include:

1. Flexibility and non-violence. Soft power and public diplomacy are based on the use of peaceful means to achieve goals rather than hard power and violence.

2. Attraction and Persuasion – Soft power and public diplomacy seek to create a positive impression of a country or organization in order to attract the support of allies, partners and public opinion.

3. Effectiveness in conflict resolution – the use of diplomacy and the use of “soft power” often helps resolve conflicts and reduce tensions between parties.

4. Long-term outcome – soft power and public diplomacy strategies are usually aimed at establishing stable relationships, establishing long-term cooperation and achieving sustainable development.

5. Importance of Communication – Effective use of communication channels, information sharing and networking are important for the successful implementation of soft power and public diplomacy strategies.

It is known everyone that Uzbekistan is located in the center of Central Asia and cooperates with its neighbors in all areas. This, in turn, is very important for the country’s economic growth and the formation of its soft power. Uzbekistan's foreign policy aims to strengthen relations with neighboring countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan and establish cooperation programs with them. Chinese scholar Meng Honghua said that Joseph Nye's research served as the basis for the emergence and development of the concept of "soft power" in China. Scholars in China have been studying the concept of soft power, writing academic papers, and developing ways to promote it in their country since the 1990s. Today, China's soft power underpins its stable economy and foreign policy.

Uzbekistan has established extensive trade relations with China and follows its policies. Another foreign trade partner of Uzbekistan is Türkiye. This country also uses the “soft power” model in politics. Turkey's soft power potential stems from its history, culture and geography. Instead of viewing them as an obstacle or a burden, the Turks are now turning them into a strategic asset in both domestic and foreign policy. In addition to establishing relations with new regions, Turkey continues relations with its old allies, developing new soft power capabilities and various elements of strategic communications in the regional and global context. The mission of Turkish diplomacy is to tell the whole world a new history of Turkey. Rapid changes in Turkey's internal and external dynamics are manifesting themselves in different ways and creating new opportunities as well as risks. By reconnecting with its history and geography, Turkey is leaving behind the one-dimensional and reductionist views of the Cold War (World War II) era with the slogan that time and space are strategically important in a globalized world. From foreign policy, economics and public policy to education, media, arts and science, Turkey is trying to present itself as an active player in demanding global changes in center-periphery relations to create a more democratic and fair world system. The result of these reforms can be called the emergence of “Turkish restaurants”, factories for the production of “Turkish textiles”, built in all countries of Central Asia. Due to this industry, the culture and history of the Turks are widely disseminated. This pattern should also be analysed. “The changes taking place in Turkish society and foreign policy are caused by cracks in the regional and global system, as well as those occurring in Turkey itself. Turkey, which has become one of the important actors in the regional order and global system, is experiencing these changes along with its own life. Thus, it would be correct to say that a “new Turkish history” is emerging. The changes brought about by Turkey's internal dynamics and their influence on foreign policy are visible on a large scale. From Europe to America, from the Middle East to Asia, from international relations to political science and cultural studies, new

discussions about Turkey have returned. These new dynamics, emerging from recent episodes of Turkish modernization, add new dimensions to Turkey's traditional relations with Europe and the United States. A new Turkey is emerging, with a new geopolitical vision on the one hand, and Turkish economic and security priorities on the other. Tectonic changes in Turkish foreign policy cannot be explained either by ideological considerations or by considerations of realpolitik. Turkey's soft power potential is explained as a combination of the country's history, geography, cultural depth, economic strength and democracy, and its role in Turkey's foreign policy is highlighted. Since the establishment of the Office of Public Diplomacy under the Prime Minister of Turkey, public diplomacy, which is a platform for the implementation of soft power, is a new concept in Turkey and is especially discussed more and more. According to politician Nye, there are three ways to achieve your goal: threaten the other side and, if necessary, start a war; “ransom of the other party; persuading the other side using soft power. It is persuading the other side with convincing arguments and wise politics. Here trust and persuasion are key elements of soft power. Soft power potential of the country determines the success of its society, as do the diplomacy, integrity and effectiveness of its policies. Based on a “value” definition of power, soft power explains how attractive and worthy a country is perceived to be. According to Nye, soft power “explains the attractiveness of a country's culture, political concepts and policies. The perceived legitimacy of a country's policies also determines that country's soft power potential.

What are the potential of “soft power” and the importance of “soft power” in Uzbekistan at present time? It is considered as the time has come to develop a “soft power” strategy in Uzbekistan’s foreign policy. Till today there wasnt such strategy. There are also a number of problems and obstacles to developing such a strategy. We have the resources, but no mechanism to develop such a power strategy. Until now, Uzbekistan has not fully applied the “soft power” model in foreign policy. Therefore, if we talk about the potential of “soft power”, there are several student and teacher exchange programs with the aim of spreading the Uzbek language and culture in Central Asia. Cooperation programs have been established with the Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies in Uzbekistan, the Bishkek State University named after K. Karasaeva in Kyrgyzstan, the Kyrgyz-Turkish Manas University, which ranks 851 in international rankings, and the National University of Tajikistan. He also established cultural ties with the Azerbaijani state. In 2023, the Center for Uzbek Language and Culture named after Alisher Navoi opened in Azerbaijan. The center runs courses and projects in the Uzbek language and crafts. Uzbekistan's soft power potential is not limited to Central Asian countries, but has also reached countries such as the United States, China, Germany, Russia and Italy. China is one of Uzbekistan’s main export and import partners, and the volume of trade relations between them in 2023 amounted to about 14,000,000,000 US dollars. Germany and Italy have allocated quotas for Uzbek master's and doctoral students at their most prestigious universities.

Uzbekistan can show its “soft power” in education, culture, sports, economics, tourism and other areas. The soft power of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes cultural, educational and humanitarian aspects that serve to strengthen the international prestige and influence of the country. This could include the promotion of Uzbek culture, language and art, as well as cooperation in the fields of education, science and sports. Soft power plays an important role in diplomatic relations and allows a country to establish partnerships with other countries based on the exchange of knowledge and values. Today we have many shortcomings in promoting and glorifying our cultural and historical heritage on the world stage. For example, Uzbekistan actively

collaborated with UNESCO from its independence until 2000. But later this relationship cooled down. After all, this organization is the most important organization that increases the cultural attractiveness of Uzbekistan in the world. But today the dynamics have dropped.

Education, widespread propaganda of the Uzbek language and literature abroad is a pressing issue of state policy. For the further development of this area, it is necessary to translate the works of representatives of Uzbek classical and modern literature, organize different international projects, increase the number of educational grants in higher educational institutions and create conditions for the study and work of foreign students. Attracting them to Uzbekistan by allocating grants for foreign students will give effective results. We can see this in the examples of Turkey and Germany. Turkish and German language courses are compulsory in the first year of study. As a result, Uzbek culture is formed among foreign students through the Uzbek language.

Culture, by ensuring of which the regularity of classical music and dance festivals and concert programs in Uzbekistan. It is possible to promote musical culture more widely by improving the quality and compelling content of Uzbek music and songs and social networks, and creating modern audio programs. It is known to everyone that at present time projects dedicated to the musical traditions of Azerbaijan, an active country in this field, are becoming popular.

Video sports, this direction is the basis of “soft power” in Uzbekistan. Further development of the industry will increase the prestige of the Uzbek name in the international arena.

Economy, in order to increase the volume of GDP (gross domestic product), applying the experience of foreign enterprises and increasing export volumes are the main tasks for the future. Today, business is in full swing promoting the Uzbek brand on a large scale, supporting confidence in the product. Efforts to attract investors are paying off.

Tourism, Uzbekistan has its own rich and unique history. This is one of our achievements in the tourism sector. But there are a number of things that need to be done. One of them is the improvement of monuments in Surkhandara, Navoi, Tashkent regions and other regions, except for the cities of Bukhari, Samarkand, Khiv, attracting tourists and creating a comfortable tourist environment.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, it should be summarized that Uzbekistan actively participates in international relations. Platforms such as the UN, SCO, CIS and C5+1 can become a tool for Uzbekistan to demonstrate its image. “The location of our republic in the center of Central Asia opens up many opportunities. It is located in the center of the region and allows it to play the role of a transit country for trade and transport between Asia, Europe and the Middle East. “Participation as a transit zone in “One Place, One Road”, “North-South” and other major projects will lead to the spread of “soft power”. To develop soft power in the future, Uzbekistan should invest in quality teaching of its language.

Foreign students and teachers should not face any obstacles in learning the Uzbek language. In this way, it will be possible to promote the Uzbek language and culture at the international level. Expanding the scope of Uzbekistan’s economic cooperation will also contribute to the further development of its “soft power”.

In Uzbekistan, there is a great need to study the concept of “soft power”, research should be carried out. Thanks to the research, new opportunities are created for studying the “soft power” of Uzbekistan and recommendations are made.

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